
The Perceived Inequalities in Resource Allocation in Multi-Campus Universities in Ghana: The Case of University for Development Studies and Presbyterian University of Ghana

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ABSTRACT: This paper examined and compared the resource allocation mechanisms in two multi-campus universities (MCUs) in Ghana. They are University for Development Studies (UDS) and Presbyterian University College, Ghana (PUCG), now known as Presbyterian University, Ghana (PUG). The main objective of the study was to investigate the perceived inequalities in the allocation of resources among the various campuses of the two Universities. The qualitative method, comparative case study approach and in-depth interview techniques were used to conduct the research. In all, eight senior management members (Pro Vice-Chancellors; Registrars; and Campus Heads) of the two Universities were purposively selected and interviewed. The findings revealed that these Universities do not have an established formula for the allocation of infrastructural and human resources for their respective campuses. It was also found that they use some percentages/ratios-based formula for the allocation of funds to the campuses. The paper recommends that physical infrastructure and human resources should be allocated based on deficits identified through need assessments. Secondly, to ensure a fair allocation of funds to the various campuses of the two universities, the deployment of a standardised mathematical formula is recommended.

KEYWORDS- Education, Development, Single Campus, Multi Campus, Quality, University

I. INTRODUCTION

The increasing demand for tertiary or higher education, coupled with limited access to Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in the 21st Century, is a key factor driving the restructuring of these institutions into Multi-Campus Universities (MCUs) so as to ensure efficient operations and access to education. These objectives made the management of many Single Campus Universities (SCUs) or HEIs across the globe to embark on restructuring programmes in order to meet the demands and expectations of prospective students, parents and guardians (Dinye and Boon, 2023). In other words, the emergence of MCUs in recent times in many parts of the world is principally a strategy to mitigate the deficits in access to higher education attributed the SCUs (Becker, 2015; McGuinness, 1991). According to McGuinness (1991), MCUs emerged in the governance and management landscape of HEIs during the early turn of the 20th Century, but could not survive the adverse effects of the Great Depression. However, the MCU model resurfaced in the early 1960s (McGuinness, 1991; Lee & Bowen, 1971) and has been improved and sustained over the past decades. Gade (1993) also observed that MCUs currently dominate the landscape of higher education. For example, they control more than half of the total students admitted into public HEIs in the United States. In fact, the Multi-Campus University System (MCUS) is extensively adopted and implemented by most colleges and universities in USA and China. It has therefore become a 21st Century model for HEIs and is widely embraced and recognised by both public and private universities across the globe (Becker, 2015).

Generally, MCUs refer to universities and HEIs that have two or more campuses offering tertiary education programmes and are governed by a single mission and centralised administration. (Wu & Wu, 2013). For some scholars, the Central Administration (CA) in an MCU usually has oversight responsibility for determining the governing structures and outlining responsibilities for the various campuses to achieve goal congruence and synergy in the entire university (Ardis et al., 2013; Gumprecht, 2007). Besides, French (2003), Willoughby (2003) and Johnstone (1999) also describe MCUs as universities or colleges with a number

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of dispersed campuses or branches that are structured around a CA which is responsible for the coordination and management functions, except the provision of services relating to teaching and learning. The MCUs often have a complex governance or management structure as compared to the SCUs, which do not have campuses geographically located from them.

As has already been mentioned, MCUs are often adopted and established to broaden educational opportunities and access but also to address local communities' demands and need for human resource development. For instance, research by Greenberg et al. (2008), Deakin University (2009), Sheth et al. (2013), Harman (2006), Elson-Green (2006), and Lynch (2003) indicate that MCUs are designed to provide equal access to education for all students, communities, and regions. They suggest that MCUs enhance the lives and economic well-being of indigenous people, encourage diversity among students, faculty, and community members, and thereby remove unfair barriers to higher education in remote and rural places. The MCUs model generally facilitates and enhances decentralisation of resources (human, physical, and financial), facilities and services to the geographically dispersed campuses (Griffith University, 2005; Scott et al., 2007). However, the American Association of University Professors (2006), Harman & Harman (2003), Willoughby (2003), and French (2003) argue that the MCUs model only allows for the decentralisation of academic services, human resources and basic consumables to the dispersed campuses according to their projected needs, while the overall management of major resources and the campuses is centralised at the CA.

In recent times, both public and private MCUs have begun to show up in most parts of Ghana. For instance, the Government of Ghana established the University for Development Studies (UDS) as a MCU in 1992 and mandated it to "blend the academic world with that of the community in order to provide constructive interaction between the two for the total development of Northern Ghana, in particular, and the country as a whole" (PNDC Law 279, Section 2). According to Effah (1998), UDS was "borne out of the new thinking in higher education which emphasizes the need for universities to play a more active role in addressing problems of the society, particularly in the rural areas". Thus, the UDS has four campuses, seven Faculties, one Business School, one Medical School, one Graduate School, and three Centres. The four campuses are distributed across three Regions in Northern Ghana: Wa Campus is sited in the Upper West Region; Navrongo Campus is established in the Upper East Region; and Tamale and Nyankpala Campuses are situated in the Northern Region (UDS, 2016). However, the focus of this study is on the CA located in Tamale and the Wa and Navrongo Campuses which are situated in Wa and Navrongo respectively. The authors admit that the two campuses of UDS selected for the study have been converted into autonomous universities by the Government in 2019 and named as SD Dombo University of Business and Integrated Development Studies (SDD-UBIDS) (Republic of Ghana, 2019) and C. K. Tandem University of Technology and Applied Sciences (CKT-UTAS) (Republic of Ghana, 2019).

The origin and structure of the second MCU examined in this case study is the Presbyterian University College of Ghana (PUCG). The Synod of the Presbyterian Church of Ghana took a decision in 1996 to found PUCG and this led to its establishment in 2003. The principal reason for this initiative was a "response to the challenge presented by the high demand for student admission in Ghanaian universities (low access), the perceived lowering of academic standards and the erosion of moral and ethical values in the Ghanaian Society" (PUCG, 2016). The mandate of PUCG is also aims to "relate its programmes to the developmental needs of Ghana in the 21st Century and beyond, in terms of training, research and extension services. It will identify and fill important niches in the development of higher education in the country" (PUCG, 2016). The PUCG has five campuses dispersed across three regions in southern Ghana as follows: Okwahu and Akwapem Campuses both in the Eastern Region; Asante-Akyem and Kumasi Campuses in the Ashanti Region; and Tema Campus, in the Greater Accra Region. However, only the CA located in Abetifi-Kwahu, the Tema Campus situated in Tema, and the Asante-Akyem Campus sited in Agogo were covered in the paper. The authors acknowledge that the PUCG has now been renamed as Presbyterian University of Ghana (PUG) after it received a Presidential Charter to operate as fully-fledged University in 2022 (PUG, 2023).

II. PROBLEM STATEMENT AND OBJECTIVES

MCUs across the globe face a number of teething challenges and complex governance and management structures. They are often bogged down with perceptions of mistrust, inequalities and unfair sharing of resources and provision of essential services by the Main campus or CA (Dhliwayo, 2014; Liu and Lv, 2007; Gaither, 1999). These perceptions by campus staff of MCUs are influenced by the way the centralised administrations are managed. In addition, the problems of distance and inequitable allocation of resources are potential threats to the survival and sustainable development of MCUs, especially in developing countries like Ghana. It is against this backdrop that this paper investigated the perceived mistrust and inequalities in the distribution of resources in MCUs in Ghana using the University for Development Studies (UDS) and the Presbyterian University of Ghana (PUG) as a case study.

The main objective of the paper was to investigate the perceived mistrust and inequalities in the allocation of resources among the campuses of public and private MCUs in the highly competitive higher education environment in Ghana. The study specifically examined how financial, physical and human resources are allocated to the various campuses of two MCUs. The paper recommends a number of pathways to enable the two case studied universities and other existing MCUs in Ghana and

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elsewhere to build and develop robust resource allocation models or mechanisms that guarantee fairness, equity and the highest research and education quality standards. According to Dinye and Boon (2023), the central administrations (CAs) of MCUs need to adopt relevant management principles and effective governance systems to improve the performance of MCUs. The practice of good governance, transparency, accountability, and participatory leadership is fundamental for the survival and sustainability of MCUs in Ghana. The findings of this paper constitute a significant contribution to literature, knowledge and scholarship on the management of MCUs in Ghana and the need to deploy robust, fair and equitable resource allocation models.

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Definition of Multi-Campus University System

According to Lee and Bowen (1971), an MCU is one that has a well-coordinated management structure to oversee its campuses and peripheral institutions that offer higher education with a special focus on the community. Wu and Wu (2013) describe an MCU as a university or a college which has two or more campuses or branches that offer four-years higher education programmes and is managed by a single or centralised management body. In a similar vein, other scholars define MCU as a university which has more than two geographically dispersed campuses or branches where each of them holds a substantial student population (Charles, 2009; Scott et al., 2007; Griffith University, 2005; and French, 2003). In addition, an MCU is also regarded as a university or college in which academic services, resources and basic facilities are decentralised to the campuses based on their estimated needs, while management of the major resources is centralised at the Central Administration (CA) also known as the Main Campus (Dhliwayo, 2014; American Association of University Professors, 2006; Willoughby, 2003). Again, Dengerink (2001) and Johnstone (1999) suggest that the basic distinguishing characteristics of between MCU and SCU are the campuses and centralised management located at the CA. Also, Creswell et al. (1985) identify the following defining characteristics of MCUs to include a) being publicly or privately owned and controlled; b) having a single or one governing board; c) having campuses which are like multiple type institutions; and d) being managed and coordinated by one Central Administration.

The working definition of an MCU adopted in this paper is a public or private university with two or more geographically dispersed campuses or branches that are overseen and managed centrally with the goal of providing communities and potential students easy access to higher education. The MCU system is a contemporary structure of higher education institutions that is widely accepted and adopted by management of both public and private universities in both the developed and developing countries (Becker, 2015). MCUs play significant roles in expanding access to higher education to prospective students, especially in the rural or remote areas in the world. Thus, the campuses are often located far away from the main campus, but are required to report to the former (the main campus) which is responsible for exercising oversight duties and the general coordination and management of the whole university (French, 2003; Willoughby, 2003). Dinye and Boon (2023) suggest that “the MCUS is mostly adopted and operated by public or private universities for the purposes of maximising the use of the available limited resources; making higher or tertiary education accessible and closer to rural communities and students; expanding educational facilities and market share; and also for depopulating the main campus.” According to Harman (2006), the MCU system encourages and promotes diversity, specialisation, national integration and cohesion, and ensures regional balance in the provision of higher education. The MCU’s centralised management system helps to guarantee consistent quality standards are enforced across all campuses irrespective of whether they are located in urban or rural areas.

B. Resource Allocation in Multi-Campus University System

The allocation of physical, human and financial resources among the dispersed campuses of an MCU is often a very difficult task for the CA mainly because of the competing needs and demands of the campuses. Liu and Lv (2007) posit that most MCUs are often faced with challenges in the distribution and sharing of physical or infrastructural, human and financial resources across the various campuses. According to Scott et al. (2007, p.19) “If a university has six campuses, then its resources such as libraries, student laboratories, network infrastructure, student centres and other services must be replicated, or distributed in new ways known to be effective if quality is to be consistent. This requires a higher level of both staff and non-staff expenditure to ensure equivalent quality to students wherever they study.” According to Dhliwayo (2014, p.326), “The fair sharing of resources and support in the multi-campus situation is a tricky issue.” Gaither (1999) observed that it is impossible for the campuses of an MCU to be of the same size and or have the same workloads; consequently, these differences often make it extremely difficult for MCUs to allocate their limited resources fairly. A plausible conclusion from Gaither’s (1999) observation is that it is normal for one of the campuses to become large, control more resources and become well-resourced than the other campuses in the university. Blythe (2006) cautioned that the disproportionate ownership and control of resources by campuses may create competition among them and may result in suspicions, hatred, ill-feeling and discrimination among students and staff alike. In other words, resource allocation among campuses is an important issue for MCUs and must be handled objectively and professionally.

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Mathebula and de Beer (2003) also reveal that the staff of the CA often tend to downgrade and disrespect their counterparts at the programmes and campus levels. This often influences the CA to practise unfair and inequitable allocation of resources to the campuses. Hence, Allison and Eversole (2008) and Gaskell (2011) asserted that the branches or campuses of MCUs usually suffer most in times of financial difficulties where budgets and costs are being cut or reduced. Obviously, the main campus, which is mostly responsible for the allocation of resources, may allocate more to itself at the expense of the campuses. To overcome these challenges, MCUs should engage in active consultations with the campuses so as to identify and agree on objective resource allocation criteria and model that is acceptable to all the campuses. This will help to avoid the possibility of skewing resources to one campus at the expense of the others.

C. Resource Allocation Challenges in Multi-Campus University Systems

MCUs are usually challenged in the provision of equal or similar, affordable, and accessible infrastructural facilities and other resources across the various campuses to meet or match the desired standards and quality of the main campus (Bundy, 1998; Crevald, 2001; Lynch, 2003). This poses a major challenge to many MCUs because they are often new and less resourced as compared to the traditional old SCUs (Scott et al., 2007). Again, Ezarik (2009) asserts that MCUs often face difficulties in maintaining and ensuring consistency across all the campuses so as to make the campuses attractive and competitive. Thus, most campuses do not have the requisite resources and opportunities to attract both staff and students. This mostly places the campuses as second choice institutions (Allison and Eversole, 2008).

In addition, Winchester and Sterk (2006) observed that the campuses are often prone to some levels of marginalisation, relegation, exploitation, fragmentation, duplication, inconsistency and inequity in the allocation and management of resources. These problems or challenges can be solved by a) instituting effective leadership or management systems; b) establishing efficient communication systems; and c) allocating resource equitably across all the campuses of the university. Furthermore, Mathebula and de Beer (2003) indicated that staff of the main campus often tend to be arrogant towards the campus colleagues and this adversely affects the inequity in the distribution of resources. The campuses usually suffer most in times of financial difficulties where budgets and costs are being cut or reduced (Allison and Eversole, 2008; Gaskell, 2011). The campuses located in rural areas suffer from more drastic cost or budget cuts compared to those that are urban-based.

IV. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

The determination and deployment of transparent methods and formulae for effective and efficient allocation and distribution of physical, human, and financial resources to the campuses of an MCU by the main campus or CA requires effective stakeholder consultations and proper needs assessment. This would lead to judicious sharing and usage of the limited resources. As is illustrated in the conceptual framework depicted in Figure 1, the allocation of resources to the campuses by the main campus of an MCU should aim to ensure equity and fairness and devoid of inequalities, arbitrariness, and discrimination. This would guarantee motivation and commitment of staff and students to worker harder and improve the quality of research and teaching across the campuses. Ultimately, the efficiency, competitiveness, and attractiveness of the MCU as first choice institution will become a reality. Thus, where the main campus engages and effectively consults the campuses on the allocation of resources in a fair and equitable manner will significantly influence the performance of the campuses and the university in general. On the other hand, where unilateral and arbitrary decisions are taken by the main campus on the allocation of resources, negative perceptions, demotivation and decline in performance will be the end result. The relationship among the relevant resource allocation variables and the projected outcomes are presented in the conceptual framework illustrated in Figure 1 below:

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework, Source: Framework relating the main variables of the study

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V. METHODS, RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Methods

The UDS Central Administration and its Navrongo and Wa Campuses and the PUG Central Administration and its Asante-Akyem and Tema Campuses were purposely selected and case studied. The qualitative research approach was employed for collecting and analysing data from respondents from these two MCUs. The four campuses were purposely chosen because they are far from the Main Campuses. The study used a comparative case study research design. According to Campbell (2010) and Kaarbo and Beasley (1999), this study design thoroughly investigates and contrasts the context and aspects of two or more distinct events. Structured interviews were conducted with eight respondents from the two institutions, including one Pro Vice-Chancellor, one Vice President, two Registrars, and four Deans-in-Charge/Deans. The data obtained were reduced, presented, and conclusions derived and confirmed using Miles and Huberman's (1994) three step qualitative data analysis.

B. Results and Discussion

Allocation of Funds:

Majority (62.5%) of the respondents noted that allocation of funds to the campuses is basically driven by the projected needs of the campuses, and the student numbers. Besides, some other respondents (37.5%) indicated that the distribution of funds could also be influenced by lobbying skills, the nature of programmes, and the availability of funds. Thus, one of the respondents enumerated a number of factors that influence the allocation of funds:

"We look at the infrastructure needs, then they also look at numbers – student numbers, then they also look at strategic programmes like medical school if you are talking of numbers they do not have numbers, but the allocation there is always big." (RDW, Tuesday, 26th April, 2016)

Again, another respondent observed as follows:

"The nature of the need, the exigence of the need, the resource availability, and the lobbying ability of officers." (RDT, Wednesday, 6th April, 2016)

All the four respondents selected from the PUCG categorically stated that the university does not employ and use any formula in the allocation of funds to the campuses. From the responses of the participants, it is obvious that they are desirous for a formula to be applied in the distribution of funds, but RDT explained that:

"The reason is that we are still growing and some of the campuses are still developing. We do not have enough resources in terms of revenue generation and therefore if you have a laid down formula that is rigid it will disadvantage studies." (RDT, Wednesday, 6th April, 2016)

However, all the four respondents drawn from the UDS stated that the university uses a formula for the distribution of funds to the campuses. The respondents described the composition and application of the formula. However, an RDN clearly explained that:

"Now the formula which has been in use for the past three years or so looks at a percentage across board all the academic facility user fees are put together then a percentage is allocated for disbursement to the faculties, then a flat percentage of this percentage shared equally among the faculties and schools, then after the remaining percentage is shared according to the number of students that you have. For instance, they may keep let's say 50% of all the total amounts collected as academic facility user fees 50% may be kept in the CA then the remaining 50% is available for disbursement to all the faculties and schools then this 50% let's say 40% is shared equally among all schools and faculties which means that whether you have students or not you will get something then the remaining 60% of the 50% is now shared according to students numbers so, there is some level of cross subsidisation to take care of faculties which don't have many students. Again, 7% of the total amount of each of the faculties is taken for the general administration of the campus." (RDN, Friday, 13th May, 2016)

Thus, upon a critical examination of the above description and illustration of the UDS' formula, the following mathematical formula has been formulated:

$$TF = RC + W_1 \frac{(TF - RC)}{n} + \sum_{i=1}^n (100 - W_1) \frac{n_i}{N} (TF - RC)$$

Figure 2: Proposed Formula for Allocation of Funds

Source: Fieldwork (May, 2016)

Where:

TF = total fees

TF – RC = amount available for disbursement to faculties

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$RC = w_0TF$ (amount retained by the centre – for Central and Campus management)

W_0 = the percentage of total fees retained by the centre

W_1 = the percentage of the amount available for disbursement that is shared equally

n = the number of faculties

N = the total number of students

n_i = the number of students in the i th faculty

Notwithstanding the existence and application of a formula in the allocation of funds in MCUs, the campuses usually suffer most in times of financial difficulties where budgets and costs are to be cut or reduced (Allison and Eversole, 2008; Gaskell, 2011). This is obvious because the CA is always responsible for the allocation funds and hence will allocate more to itself at the expense of the campuses. This result confirms the view of Dhliwayo (2014), Liu and Lv (2007) and Gaither (1999) that achieving fair distribution of resources in MCUs is a major challenge.

It is important that PUCG takes a cue from the UDS resource allocation model so as to reduce or avoid the current arbitrary and discretionary allocation of funds to the faculties and schools. However, it is necessary to point out a principal weakness of the formula used by the UDS is that does not ensure sufficient allocation of funds to the campuses and the office of the campus heads.

Allocation of Infrastructure:

Although all the respondents agreed that the allocation of infrastructure (such as lecture halls, auditoriums, laboratories, libraries, halls of residence for both staff and students, etc.) is fundamentally driven by the needs of the campuses and faculties, they also identified factors such as student numbers, availability of funds, and new programmes as influencing the allocation of infrastructure as well. However, few of the respondents also identified the discretion of top management as one of the criteria of the allocation. For instance, RDW responded unequivocally thus:

“It is based on discretion of the people [management] at the top there.” (RDW, Tuesday, 26th April, 2016)

Another respondent, RPV in responding to the question on the factors considered in the allocation of infrastructure opined that:

“..... we just look at the needs for those things and our WPD will go and do some quantity estimates and funds are made available. It depends on the needs of the faculties and the timing.” (RPV, Monday, 11th April, 2016)

Another respondent observed that:

“It will all depend still on the need for those resources and availability of funds.” (RDT, Wednesday, 6th April, 2016)

However, all the respondents of both universities confirmed that no formula is used for the allocation of infrastructure to the campuses. A number of reasons provided for this situation. For instance, a respondent, RPV observed that:

“It will be difficult. So if we have a formula, I do not think it will augur well for efficient allocation of resources. As in that case, we do not have, we only spend within our resources. I think that is the most important thing.” (RPV, Monday, 11th April, 2016)

One of the participants also responded thus:

“The reason is that we are still growing some of the campuses are still developing. We do not have enough resources in terms.....” (RDT, Wednesday, 6th April, 2016)

In addition, another respondent noted in his response that:

“For establishing infrastructure, there is no formula. But it is based on need, so that is the general formula – is based on need of the various campuses approved by the Development Committee (DC).” (RRU, Monday, 11th April, 2016)

In line with the suggestion by Dhliwayo (2014), Liu and Lv (2007) and Gaither (1999) that achieving fair distribution of resources in MCUs is vital, it is imperative that the two case-studied universities should consider devising an appropriate model for the allocation infrastructure to the campuses. The management of the universities should draw inspiration from the following observation by Scott et al. (2007, p.19): “If a university has six campuses, then its resources such as libraries, student laboratories, network infrastructure, student centres and other facilities must be replicated, or distributed in new ways known to be effective if quality is to be consistent.”

Recruitment:

According to the respondents, recruitment in the two universities is not conducted entirely by any one particular individual or officer, but through a participatory and consultative process involving all the relevant stakeholders, such as Sectional Heads, Deans, and HODs. The respondents of both universities acknowledged the vital role of the Registrar in the recruitment process in his capacity as the Chief Administrator of the university. They emphasised that the final selection is normally done by an appropriate committee. An RDT noted that the recruitment process in the university is anchored on the appointment committees.

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“We have two appointment committees: one for senior members, and one for senior and junior staff. So, it will be referred to the appropriate committee for interviews and recommendations.” (RDT, Wednesday, 6th April, 2016)

Besides, RRU provided an elaborate and detailed descriptions of the entire recruitment process and emphasised that the recruitment process is handled by the Registrar, but the appointment of the applicants is determined by the appropriate appointment and promotion committee:

“..... we have Appointment and Promotion Board (A&P) which is for senior members, and Appointment and Promotion Committee (APC) for senior and junior staff. The Deans determine the qualifications and need for applicants before the appropriate appointment committee invites them for the interview.” (RRU, Monday, 11th April, 2016)

RDN in his response also testified that the recruitment process is participatory because it involves the Deans and HODs of the respective faculties and departments the applicants are recruited for, but thought otherwise about the effectiveness of the participation:

“..... sometimes you have an application letter on your desk you have not worked on and the applicant has been invited for interview.” (RDN, Friday, 13th May, 2016)

However, it was revealed that the campuses do not have the authority to conduct recruitment because staff are normally recruited into the university and not the campus. Thus, the overall responsibility for recruitment resides with the CA or top management through centralised appointment committees. For instance, RDT stated that:

“We have one centralised appointments committee. We don't have campuses doing appointments.” (RDT, Wednesday, 6th April, 2016)

The above statement of RDT is corroborated by RRU when he also stated that:

“..... as I said, the A&P I mentioned is one A&P for all the campuses.” (RRU, Monday, 11th April, 2016)

Another respondent, RRP highlighted that staff are recruited into the university by stating that:

“We pick them into this university and then we indicate that your first appointment is at the university or at this department, so they are recruited into the university, but they are not recruited to the campuses in the first instance.” (RRP, Wednesday, 6th April, 2016)

The responses of the respondents indicate that although the campuses or faculties play significant roles in the recruitment process of the universities, they do not have the powers or authority to recruit directly by themselves. Thus, the campuses or faculties determine the suitability of applicants, make recommendations, and partake in interviews. For instance, RPV asserted that:

“They identify suitable candidates; they prepare them and then we interview them together with them [the campuses] and then the registry then recruits and appoints.” (RPV, Monday, 11th April, 2016)

Similarly, RRP was also opined that the campuses or faculties contribute to the recruitment process because:

“They vet the candidates whether they are suitable because if the person is going to be a lecturer in any programme, then we expect the HOD to look at the application to see if the person is suitable. And then during the interview that particular head will prepare to ask the right questions, and to help us determine the suitability of the individual.” (RRP, Wednesday, 6th April, 2016)

The RRU also explained that the participation of the campuses or faculties in the recruitment process is essentially for teamwork. Hence, his assertion that:

“The role they play is to recommend to the A&P the suitability of the candidate looking at his qualification whether they require the candidate or not..... It is clearly a teamwork between the centre and the faculties. It is teamwork. The VC is the Chairman of the A&P, Academic Board has a representation on the A&P, the Dean and the HOD of the person who is going to be interviewed sit on it. They have total involvement in recruitment, but just that a dean cannot sit down and do his own recruitment. But the Dean has the right to determine who he wants to work with in his faculty that is it.” (RRU, Monday, 11th April, 2016)

It important to note that all the respondents of the two universities agreed that the campuses, faculties and departments are involved in the entire recruitment process. This makes the recruitment process transparent and participatory. It is also evident from the various responses on recruitment that the centre or top management does not single-handedly perform the entire recruitment function, but coordinates and approves the final decisions determined by the all the stakeholders. Consequently, major decisions on staffing such as recruitment, transfers, promotions, demotions and dismissals must be sanctioned by the central management (Massarik and Pei-Carpenter, 2002).

Allocation of Staff:

The allocation or posting of staff, especially administrative staff, to the various campuses has always been a very difficult task for the CA or management. Liu and Lv (2007) explain that MCUs usually have some difficulties to equitably allocate or distribute their limited resources such as human resources equitably across the dispersed campuses. One respondent indicated that based on the needs of the campuses, staff are recruited for them or transferred to them:

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“The allocation of staff to the campuses are based on the needs of the campuses and the request made by the campuses. These two are important even if they need and they do not tell us we do not know. It applies to both academic and administrative.” (RRU, Monday, 11th April, 2016)

“The vacancy would have been declared by a particular campus, so the appointment is made for that particular campus and once you are appointed, your appointment letter will indicate the campus to which you are being appointed for. However, there is the possibility of somebody to be transferred from one campus to the other when the need arises.” (RDT, Wednesday, 6th April, 2016)

“For administrative staff you can be transferred or recruited at the head office and sent to the campuses. When it comes to the academic, staff are recruited based on their skills and speciality relating to a specific campus, but administrative staff can just be reshuffled.” (RDA, Monday, 9th May, 2016)

Even though the respondents believe that staff are allocated to the campuses based on their needs and requests, the CA is likely to retain most of the best recruits and send a few and a low-grade recruits, especially, administrative staff, to the campuses. This is supported by Mathebula and de Beer's (2003) assertion that staff of the main campus of the university often tend to downgrade and disrespect their colleagues on the campuses. Allison and Eversole, (2008) observed that the campuses are regarded as second choice institutions and therefore serve as centres for disciplinary transfers, while the CA serves as a centre for reward transfers.

VI. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

A. Conclusion

The allocation of resources to the campuses of the two case studied MCUs is influenced by the needs of their, student numbers, lobbying skills, the nature of programmes, and availability of funds. Allocation of funds to the campuses in PUCG is basically influenced by the above factors because they do not have or use any formula for that purpose. On the contrary, UDS uses a formula for disbursement school fees or funds to the campuses. The formula provides for some level of cross-subsidisation to ensure that even faculties with few students are taken care of. In both universities, the allocation of infrastructure to the campuses and faculties is also influenced by the needs of the campuses and faculties, the student numbers, availability of funds, new programmes and the discretion of top management. Again, in both universities, academic and administrative staff are allocated to the campuses and faculties based on their needs and the requests submitted to the CAs. The administrative staff are normally transferred or recruited at the head office and posted to the campuses. On the other hand, the academic staff are recruited based on their skills and speciality in relation to a specific campus or faculty. Although staff are allocated to the campuses based on their needs and requests, the CA is likely to retain most of the best recruits and send a few and a low-grade recruits, especially the administrative staff, to the campuses. The campuses therefore serve as centres for disciplinary transfers, while the CA serves as a centre for reward transfers.

B. Recommendations

Compared to the traditional SCUs, the management of MCUs across the globe still remains a complex and daunting exercise because of their peculiar nature and composition. The management complexities and difficulties in MCUs are more pronounced in the developing world, especially where basic resources are woefully inadequate. There is therefore an urgent need to develop workable governance systems and structures to ensure effective and efficient management and utilisation of the scarce resources. The recommendations emanating from the findings of the paper are the following:

Although the UDS applies a formula in the allocation of resources, the amount or percentage allocated to the Campus Heads for managing their campuses is insufficient. It is therefore recommended that the said amount or percentage should be included in the amount or percentage retained by the CA and a percentage of the latter shared among the campuses according to their student numbers.

The UDS and PUCG should adopt and apply the mathematical formula presented in Figure 2 for the allocation of resources. Also, both UDS and PUCG should collate the infrastructural needs of all the campuses with the help of the Campus Heads for a period of three years and place them on a scale of preference according to priority. This would replace the arbitrary and discretionary allocation of infrastructure in the two universities.

The two universities should design packages and schemes that aim to develop the campuses to be attractive and first choice institutions to both staff and students. This would help to reverse the situation whereby the CA staff tend to downgrade and disrespect the staff of the campuses (Mathebula and de Beer, 2003). In this way, the campuses would no longer merely serve as centres for disciplinary transfers.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

This article is an extract of a Master of Philosophy thesis entitled “Managing Multi-Campus Universities in Ghana: A Comparative Analysis of University for Development Studies (UDS) and Presbyterian University College, Ghana (PUCG)”

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submitted to the University of Ghana Business School by the Corresponding Author. The thesis is deposited in the repositories of the University of Ghana and the University for Development Studies: <http://ugspace.ug.edu.gh> and <http://libcatalogue.uds.edu.gh> respectively.

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